

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO LOGICAL THINKING.

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Abstract: In this article, it is discussed how to improve the logical thinking of students studying in preschool and primary school.

Key words: Development of a child's logical thinking, Cognitive ability in preschool children, Development of mental operations, development of memory, attention, creative imagination

The main part: In preschool and elementary school age, children reach the peak of their cognitive activity, and their verbal and logical thinking rises to a new level. Imagine that your child has: a serious interest in logical and mathematical problems; Excellent cognitive abilities; He knows how to work quickly with information, easily extract its essence and remember it. Logical and correct thinking; Make a careful decision. The peak of cognitive activity (age 5-10) is the best time to develop logic and teach your child how to think! It is important for parents to remember. Thought patterns are not automatically formed in a child's head. The child should be taught deliberately, this moment should not be missed.

The thinking of preschool children initially has a visual-metaphorical character, and in the process of education it gradually turns into conceptual and verbal-logical thinking. All visual educational materials are easier to perceive and understand for preschool children and students, with great interest and pleasure in completing tasks and solving problems. We found out how to help parents, teachers and most importantly, children! We created LogicLike, an online educational platform especially for preschoolers and younger students. This site has everything you need to develop logical and critical thinking in children. The platform can be used by independent education (usually 7-8 years old) and the whole family.

Mathematical development of a child is not only the preschool child's ability to calculate and solve arithmetic problems, but also the development of the ability to see relationships and connections in the world around him and work with objects, signs, symbols. Mathematical development of a child is a long and very difficult process for a preschool child, because the formation of the basic skills of logical cognition requires not only high mental activity, but also generalized knowledge about the general and important features of objects and phenomena of reality. . . Working in a circle allows children to participate in play interactions and intellectually develops preschoolers. This can be achieved by including work related to concepts outside the scope of the program materials. Logical problems often have unexpected solutions. The formation of a creative personality will be helped by tasks that include various solutions, which will allow you to put forward hypotheses and undergo verification based on the analysis of available data. Working with missing data helps build critical thinking and mini-research skills. Completing tasks helps to increase the knowledge and skills of preschool children. The materials in the group activities include a wide range of topics, which allows preschool children to expand their knowledge in the field of cognitive development. Play-learning helps to satisfy children's natural need for recognition and exploration, their uncontrollable curiosity. Educational games are one of the means of mental development of children. It is important and interesting for children, the content is varied and very dynamic, it

can satisfy children in motor activities, movements, including manipulations with children's favorite play materials, help children use counting, correctness of movements controls. The main principles of this game - interest - knowledge - creativity - it is as effective as possible, because the game directly conveys to the child the kind, original, funny and sad language, plot of the fairy tale, funny characters or invites to an adventure. . . In each game, the child always achieves some "objective" result. Constant and progressive complications of the game ("spiral") help to keep children's activity in the zone of optimal difficulty. The development of the game creates conditions for the manifestation of creativity and stimulates the development of children's mental abilities. Adults can use this natural need to gradually involve children in more complex forms of play activities.

The importance of game development for the development of preschool children, their variety and age appropriateness can be used to solve this problem of mental development of preschool children. In developed games and exercises, children develop the basic skills of the algorithmic culture of thinking, the ability to perform actions with intelligence. With the help of logical operations, children train attention, memory and perception.

The principle of systematicity and consistency refers to the relationship between knowledge, skills and competences.

✚ □ The principle of repetition of skills and abilities is one of the most important, because as a result of several repetitions, a dynamic stereotype develops.

✚ □ Principles of active education The educational process should be built using active forms and teaching methods that help to develop children's independence, initiative and creativity (game techniques, pairs, work in small groups, individually, organization of research activities, etc.).

✚ □ Communication principles help to increase children's need for communication.

✚ □ The principle of effectiveness includes obtaining positive results of work to improve health, regardless of age and level of physical development.

✚ □ Principle of individualization - development of individual qualities by solving multi-level educational problems

✚ □ The principle of problematization - the child receives knowledge not in a finished form, but in the process of his activity.

✚ □ Principles of psychological comfort - creating a calm and friendly environment, believing in the strength of the child

✚ □ Principles of creativity - formation of the ability to find non-standard solutions

Conclusion: Teaching primary school students to think logically is one of the most important tasks of primary school teachers.

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